

Practice Abstract #3

Insights from the EARTHONE Online Workshop on Climate-Resilient Land Use

Summary

OBJECTIVES.

On 5 September 2025, an online workshop brought together the full EARTHONE consortium and invited stakeholders from each partner’s regional networks. Its purpose was to gather cross-regional perspectives on climate adaptation needs, digital readiness, barriers to implementation, and expectations for the EARTHONE tools. By hosting the session online and in English, the aim was to enable participation from policy, research, practice, SMEs and civil society across all project regions.

Figure 1. During the online workshop

RESULTS.

Participants highlighted shared climate pressures (heat, drought, flooding and erratic rainfall) and vulnerabilities (small farmers, low-income households, limited advisory support). They defined key requirements for digital climate tools –transparent, integrated data, user-friendly visuals and locally tailored recommendations– and stressed the importance of features supporting compliance (emissions tracking, climate-risk interpretation and links to EU frameworks). The online format enabled cross-sector comparison (from agriculture to forestry and regional planning), creating a common baseline for EARTHONE’s tool development.

PRACTICAL IMPLICATIONS.

To apply the EARTHONE tools effectively, participants recommended starting with a clear mapping of each organisation’s existing datasets. These may include climate observations, soil data, management logs, or municipal plans. All of them can simplify integration into the Information Factory. For practitioners with limited digital experience, the Multi-Sensing Ecosystem should be introduced gradually through small pilot cases, focusing on a minimal number of sensors to build trust in data quality.

The main identified costs relate to training time and establishing data governance rules. An additional identified problem refers to ensuring stable internet access. Benefits include shared access to harmonised data and cross-regional comparison of climate risks. When applying the Scenario Builder, users should begin with simple “what-if” analyses.

Additional information

The online workshop demonstrated that implementation across regions depends strongly on organisational capacity and clarity of responsibilities. A major facilitating element is the presence of intermediaries such as advisory services, municipal climate officers, or cooperative consultants who can translate tool outputs for end-users. An obstacle highlighted by many participants is the high variability in digital capacity. Some regions already operate advanced monitoring systems, but others rely on basic paper-based planning. This inconsistency requires multilingual formats of training materials and interfaces that accommodate both experts and newcomers.

Stakeholders also emphasised the need for long-term support structures. Concerns were raised about data accuracy, interoperability, and maintenance of digital systems, particularly in small organisations with limited staff. In the future, EARTHONE will explore how to link scientific modelling with local knowledge networks. This should allow community observations such as changes in water availability or disease emergence to inform decision-support recommendations. Participants recommended that future workshops include sector-specific sessions (e.g. forestry, mountain agriculture, peri-urban planning) to deepen practical usability. For end-users, gradual adoption remains key: starting with the Information Factory as a shared storage and communication platform, then extending to scenario analysis and AI recommendations. Simple visual summaries and clear benefits such as time saved will be essential to secure long-term uptake. The same reasoning applies to better risk anticipation or easier compliance with regulations.

Figure 2. Feedback from the participants

Useful links:

- [Blog - EARTHONE held a workshop on land use and climate action.](#)
- [Recording of the online workshop.](#)

Authors: Tomasz Braun (Lazarski University)
Ljupcho Bozhinovzki (AgFutura Technologies)